

PREMIERE –
PREPARING MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS
IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY

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Insights from emerging multi-actor proposals in Cluster 6 Horizon Europe Calls 2024

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WITH CONTRIBUTIONS FROM

Anonymous interviewees of emerging proposals

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1. INTRODUCTION: OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

PREMIERE project (WP3) has the aim to identify experiences, approaches and pathways for successful multi-actor approach (MAA) proposal development. This work was planned (Tasks 3.1 and 3.2) to include following up with five emerging MA project proposals to the EU Research and innovation programme “Horizon Europe” (HE) during the months before their formal submission.

The objective of this work was to record in real time the process of developing Horizon proposals with a multi-actor approach component which, by definition, requests the involvement of proposal actors from the initial project idea (see box below). By systematised recording of these examples, we expected to obtain real cases of proposal development stories to enrich the work of PREMIERE WP3 and WP4 that analyse the proposal development process to generate useful recommendations to future applicants and develop tools to facilitate this.

Extract of the official definition of the multi-actor approach in Horizon Europe

*(...) The genuine and sufficient involvement of such actors should take place **all over the whole course of the project**: from participation in development of the project idea, planning and experiments to implementation (...)*

In early Autumn 2023 we searched for potential proposals for the envisaged follow-up across all MAA topics included in the “Horizon Europe” Cluster 6 calls with proposal submissions due on 22 February 2024. This search was primarily based on the network of contacts of PREMIERE partners, and the, then recently opened, PREMIERE 100+ Club on LinkedIn was also used to extend the search within this wide European MAA stakeholder group. The approached proposal coordinators received a short document summarising the process proposed and its full confidentiality (Annex 7.1).

After an extensive and thorough search, a total number of four relevant proposal writers accepted to participate in the study, one of which could not follow all the process and is therefore not part of this analysis. Following this selection, the three selected proposals were each followed through four individual monthly interviews between October 2023 and January 2024, plus a final post-proposal submission evaluation meeting. According to the agreement with the proponents this report refers to Proposal #1, #2, and #3, and no further information on them or the topic of the call they applied for is disclosed. When

a reference to all three proposals is made, they are named as the “emerging proposals”.

The follow-up interviews were each conducted by a single PREMIERE team member, involving a total of two interviewers, and the interviewees were also one person per each proposal. Common interview guidelines (Annex 7.2) and reporting table (Annex 7.3) were used to compile standardised information on the development process of the emerging proposals. The interviews lasted between 30-60 minutes each (one per month).

Limitations of this study

- No proposals including Operational Groups have been followed, despite these being a priority in the Horizon Europe MAA definition.
- The perspective of only one person involved per proposal was captured during the interviews.
- The sample of followed proposals did not include any late-coming consortia due to the time when the recruitment was carried out: latecomers could not have been indicated then and later no further searches for additional emerging projects were made. We considered, in parallel, that late-coming consortia would be very time-constrained to be involved in follow-up interviews.

2. BRIEF PROFILES OF THE ANALYSED EMERGING PROPOSALS: PROCESS, TIMELINE, AND ACTIVITIES

Proposal #1 aimed to apply to an Innovation Action (IA) topic with an indicative budget of 3m€. It was initiated by two organisations from the same country, with previous collaboration experience. In the summer of 2023, the proposal grew from the first idea of a staff member of one of these two organisations, who eventually became the proposal coordinator. This coordinating organisation is an academic institution with extensive experience as a project partner and having acted as a coordinator of previous EU Horizon projects. For this proposal, the coordinator had a strong research and thematic interest to lead it, and it took the practical lead of the proposal during all the preparation process. The intensive preparation of the proposal started from a blank page in September 2023, some six months before the submission deadline. Upon the submission the consortium had grown to nine institutional partners. None of them represented an existing Operational Group, as the topic addressed by the call was not well suited for their involvement.

Proposal #2 aimed to apply to a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) topic with an indicative budget of 4,5m€. In this instance two organisations from different countries that had been partners in a previous EU Horizon project worked on the proposal from the very first moment, one from the Research and the other from the Innovation area, balancing the two components. The initial idea was first developed during September 2023 (six months before the submission date) between these two partners who took the main lead and decision-making role during the whole process, while the rest of the partners had more of a follower role. As described during the interviews, the preparation process took place in a rather informal and not too structured way. The consortium was finally formed by 13 institutional partners with an interesting clear divide between research and industry/tech profiles. No Operational Groups were involved.

Proposal #3 aimed to apply to a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) topic with an indicative budget of 3,5m€. The representative who took part in the interviews was neither the proposal coordinator, nor a co-lead, as in the case of the previous two proposals. The organisation the representative of which took part in the interviewing process was approached with an invitation to join the group working on the proposal approximately six months before the submission date. A core group of six organisations, including research institutions of varying sizes was created. They took further responsibility as work area leaders

throughout the whole project development process by having regular core group meetings and managing the arrangement of work further into work packages. The core group involved researchers, advisors, business representatives, and, to some extent, also government representatives, thus representing a high degree of diversity already in early stages of the proposal development process. The recruitment of the initial group of partners was initiated through people whom they already knew and had worked together with, thus it could be described as an extension/ continuation of the existing network. All six partners in the core group had been previously working with each other in different project configurations. The core group further reflected on other partners to invite, ensuring a comprehensive geographical coverage, as well as assessing the invitees' technical experience and the extent to which they would complement the network. The consortium finally grew to 20 institutional partners. The next element of diversity that was expected by the proposal developers was the establishment of the advisory network. There were a number of potentially associated partners beyond the consortium who were identified and named and were part of the network.

Table 1: Comparative data on the three anonymous emerging proposals reviewed

	Proposal #1	Proposal #2	Proposal #3
Topic type	<i>Innovation Action (IA)</i>	<i>Research and Innovation Action (RIA)</i>	<i>Coordination and Support Action (CSA)</i>
Topic budget per project (M €)	3	4,5	3,5
Type of partners	<i>Research, Policy implementation, Civil society</i>	<i>Research, Business</i>	<i>Research, Advisory services, Business, Government</i>
Previous collaboration	<i>Only a few partners</i>	<i>Mostly new partners, two main partners with long collaboration</i>	<i>Core group with long-term collaboration</i>
Previous Horizon experience	<i>Large, except for some partners</i>	<i>Large, except for some partners</i>	<i>Large, except for some partners</i>
Inclusion of newcomers	<i>Some</i>	<i>Mostly not</i>	<i>Mostly not</i>

3. USEFUL TIPS FROM PROPOSAL DEVELOPERS

This section on interview results is an ad-hoc list of interesting suggestions and approaches used by the reviewed proposals. They do not follow any specific order or themes, but they do arise out of the interview structure and guidelines' sections (Annex 7.2 and 7.3).

Proposal #1

- **Start** a proposal **with a small number of trustful partners**, ask appropriate questions to **experts** that you can reach out to, who have a deep understanding of recent development in the field of the proposal. With these contacts, understand the focus of the call and what you will want to do, and profile the type of multi-actor partners that you need. Once all is clear, search for the necessary partners, knowing the number of partners you need, the targeted profile for each and set a deadline to engage them. Start the search with the partners that are more difficult to identify and leave easier ones for later.
- In parallel to the steps above, create a **dialogue** with the partners as the proposal progresses, and **ensure that partners do not deviate** from the topic and the structure that was agreed.
- Develop the proposal preparation through a combination of **individual meetings with partners and full consortium meetings**, with increasing intensity (monthly, twice a month, and weekly over the last eight preparation weeks). Individual meetings of the coordinator with partners, however, will only be viable if the consortium is small.
- Include **core partners with a strong pre-existing networking position** in the respective thematic domain in the consortium to help identify further strong partners (this was particularly clear in this proposal with some highly positioned core partners).
- Be strategic and use all opportunities to identify key stakeholders in the field, persons who can help in networking, key concepts, state of the art, impact identification, etc. For example, meet experts at your hand – near to you or in your network of contacts – or participate in European events where you may **find useful information to structure your proposal**, not only at the beginning but all along and right to the day of proposal submission.

- **‘Last minute’ partners** still make sense, for example, if they bring a relevant aspect that will expand the areas of expertise covered by the proposal, as happened in this case.

- A specific **multi-actor work package** may be better coordinated by a non-research partner of a proposal. This can be combined with an **‘observatory’ mechanism** that connects the MAA work to the overall project coordination.

- **Share drafts of the proposal** with your trusted network of contacts; in this proposal the coordinator was confident in sharing beyond the consortium, to get external feedback and opinion on its quality. Some proponents prefer to keep drafts completely confidential, but the proposal who brought this recommendation found this useful and will repeat this approach in the future.

Proposal #2

- As part of the initial development, **review each bullet point in the call topic text** to identify which actors/partners should be involved. At the same time, explore how each partner profiled can contribute to project dissemination activities.

- When you need to **identify new potential partners**, scout them through conference presenters and other events alike. When looking for scientific or technical experts in specific fields or methodologies, rather ask colleagues within your own team/organisation or scientific peers in your immediate networks to point out possible partners. It should not be built just on partners identified in brokerage events.

- **Take a step-by-step approach** for the long overall proposal development process. Start with the lead partners developing a proposal with a solid sequential approach to ensure beyond the state-of-the-art level, and bring the rest of the partners in once the concept is clear, instead of starting all ensembled, with a patch of disconnected ideas. This way the research framework is fixed and, when the partners join the preparation, they can focus more on the methodologies to fill in and enrich this predefined framework.

- Practise intensive bilateral meetings with co-leaders to **answer “big” questions**.

- In this particular proposal, the **initial meeting with all partners** was planned and held less than six weeks prior to submission, when the proposal was already solid. The experience of the proponent dictates that holding

consortium meetings earlier than that ends in a proposal that is too generic and has no further depth. Prior to this consortium meeting, individual meetings by the coordinator with each partner had been held, so everyone knew what to expect at this first joint meeting.

- The **MAA was slowly incorporated into the proposal**, first between the two lead organisations, next by including an MAA-specific work package (WP) in the proposal, and finally by embedding the whole consortium into the MAA. This process facilitated the incorporation of the MAA in all aspects of the proposal, and involvement of all partners, including those less prone to the MAA methodology, in undertaking specific tasks of the MAA WP.

Proposal #3

- All through the proposal development there should be a **balanced focus on advancing different parts of the proposal** by the coordinator, including the development of the WPs along with other sections of the proposal, such as the intervention logic, the hierarchy of the objectives and, particularly, the pathways of impact.

- When managing a multi-actor group of partners, it is beneficial to have **an online calendar of upcoming meetings** during the proposal writing process that involve both the meetings of the core group, a mix of different partners, and, finally, meetings for the full partnership. The calendar provides a type of framework for structuring the meetings.

- If a proposal is first developed by a core group of partners and presented to a full consortium at later stages, the core group and coordinator must be **ready to receive feedback, including criticism** on the initial structure and content of the proposal and to incorporate it in further development of the proposal. Coordinator's openness and ability to receive criticism from the practice partners tests how well the MAA has been deployed in the proposal writing process.

- In partner recruitment, **specific requirements from the call will play a major role**. Sometimes, they can also raise some issues. For instance, it can be challenging to achieve good geographical coverage. It also raises a question if there are partners needed in each individual EU Member State (MS) or if it is sufficient if the partners have further connections with other organisations in the MSs. The consortium needs to reach an eventual compromise, considering

also such factors as the available budget and the diversity of different types of advisors (since the area of the project was agricultural advice).

- The **geographical coverage** is **addressed** through a **macro-regional approach**. Rather than attempt to have partners in all MSs, the majority of MSs will be covered and then there will be some regional partners who will have the responsibility for addressing neighbouring countries.

4. MAIN APPROACHES AND METHODOLOGIES USED IN THE PROPOSAL PREPARATION

This section synthesises the structural and most relevant procedures used by each proposal, in other words, the foundations of the proposal preparation. The relevance of the procedures mentioned herein are based on the authors' criteria, according to what was expressed in the interviews along the process. Again, these approaches are extracted from the interview registries and are not necessarily exhaustive or structured in any way.

Interviewees were specifically asked about the use of digital tools although these were not a very relevant or innovative aspect in any of the three reviewed proposals.

Proposal #1

- Use an **analytical approach** all along the proposal preparation, think well, systematise key questions and repeat them in loops. Structure proposal preparation meetings the same way.
- **Make an inventory of missing skills**, as you build up your consortium, ask continuously, which skills or multi-actors needed for the topic are still missing, until you come to completion of the consortium.
- Increase the **intensity of partner meetings**, from once a month (six months before submission) and progressing to weekly meetings (over the last two months of proposal preparation). These meetings need to be well prepared (e.g. by using a summary of developments, priority discussion points or post-meeting tasks list). This can be a more effective way to capture all key points and contributions of the partners (rather than by them individually reading the text), and especially effective for multi-actors to contribute.
- **Make use of digital tools** such as basic preparatory tools from *Microsoft* package as it is part of the coordinator infrastructure. No specific tools used to address the multi-actor approach.
- Incorporate **creative, innovative**, and at the same time **feasible** forms of planned stakeholder engagement.

Proposal #2

- Use **clear diagrams and figures to help partners** align with and concentrate on the message during the proposal preparation.
- Start with individual meetings to **bring new partners into the consortium**. Next, have partners presented to each other at a first joint meeting. The presentations also bring fresh insights to coordinators, to identify new ideas and activities that might be included in the partner's tasks. After this first meeting, send the concept note to the partners and ask them how they would like to be involved. From here on, use one-to-one messages for the most critical aspects to be discussed. In this particular proposal, not many 'big meetings' with all partners were held.
- Have a very **open approach to value capturing** for your proposal, even alliances beyond the consortium itself can be relevant and add to the MAA component, as it happened with an organisation contacted that could not be a partner, due to institutional restrictions, but offered a valuable tool to contribute to the project tasks.
- **Budget management**¹ with partners was particular in the sense that the leaders decided not to disclose the budget distribution until the very last days before proposal submission. Very rigorous definition of tasks was ensured prior to fixing each partner's budget. This can be a drawback for certain reasons, but it is also a strategy to keep interest and focus for the partners. When the budget was communicated, its fairness was clear and the number of PM (Person-months) distribution between partners was well balanced. There were no complaints or discussions on budget distribution once it was shared, as sufficient funds were available for all the research involved in the proposal.
- Make the **main proposal text** (Part B) **fully available** to partners during all the writing process.
- **Use in-house resources** (expert staff) during the proposal preparation, particularly in MAA. This approach is possible given that the coordinator of the proposal has such support in their organisation, otherwise it has to be sought elsewhere.

¹ This aspect is not directly related to MAA, but it is included here as a significant aspect regarding more administrative tasks that are relevant in general, thus also for MAA proposals.

Proposal #3

- Use a **concept note** to reflect upon and a PowerPoint presentation giving initial focus for brainstorming already in the first meeting.
- Develop a strong **core group** of partners. The core group consists of potential work area leaders and during the first steps of the proposal development process gathers for regular online meetings to discuss three aspects during its internal meetings: the internal logic of the project, the preliminary discussions about WPs, and the continued development of the consortium. A **hierarchy of objectives** is being set up and double-checked with other colleagues.
- Build trust through developing a sense of **internal democracy**. It is important for smaller entities to feel that when they speak up their voice is being listened to.
- Because of the lump-sum approach, **the development of content is intertwined with the administrative work**. The proposal is divided into six work areas and inside each work area there are two to three WPs. Work area leaders have been defining the work areas in terms of their objectives and inside the work areas the logic connecting to the WPs. Looking also at interactions between work areas and work packages is important. It is a good proposal writing practice (while not necessarily a multi-actor one).
- The **time allocated** to the proposal writing will depend on the experience of partners and the coordinator's prior experience with the thematic domain of the project call. The most successful proposals are those which have been developed over time and allow multiple processes to take place, especially with respect to the newcomers. A good coordinator will understand that one needs to invest time in the capacity of less experienced partners while not slowing down the process being undertaken by more experienced partners.
- **Ensure the strength of three supporting pillars: the interpretation of the multi-actor approach, the understanding of the lump-sum principles, and the technical support**. The experience of the supporting organisation of the coordinator can be a big strength. In this case, the organisation has prepared a lot of supporting material for the partners in the form of templates and came with a very clear initial vision for how to interpret the call text in the context of the lump-sum approach.
- Ensure manifestation of a **democratic approach/ inclusive work process when allocating responsibilities**. The supporting organisation was

very keen that all partners who had expressed the interest in leading a work package, whether they had developed it or not, took the responsibility of leading one or more tasks.

5. LESSONS LEARNT: THREATS, CHALLENGES, BARRIERS, AND ADOPTED SOLUTIONS

Unexpected circumstances of many kinds may appear in a long preparatory process of large budget proposals with partners scattered across Europe and beyond. The three emerging proposals faced several of these kinds of circumstances and looked for different solutions for them. This section, more than the rest, reflects real life situations that simply emerged during the proposal preparation process. In this section the three proposals remain totally anonymous.

- **‘Loneliness of the leader - I’.** A proposal coordinator (leader) has to assume circumstances where other partners, and other multi-actors, wait for instructions, for definition of activities and deliverables, for example, and no one else is there to think with the coordinator, who has to take all on his/her shoulders. The coordinator may as well be the only one with an overall vision of the proposal to ensure coherence and absence of errors. Engaging partners is key to overcoming this.

- **‘Loneliness of the leader - II’.** There was a sense of loneliness as the scientific lead of the proposal had to develop all literature reviews (necessary to go beyond the state-of-the-art) to elaborate the excellence part and cover the social science component. Despite a good collaboration between co-leads of a proposal, still a clash of interests between social sciences and the technological part was evident and present.

- **The lump-sum approach generates new challenges.** For instance, one proposal realised in its early stages of the proposal writing process that the project should take into account the lump-sum principles, i.e. it has to be divided on the basis of work areas that have to be further divided into WPs. Accordingly, the core group was selected not as WP leaders but as work area leaders. It is a more complex approach where preliminary structuring needs to be done before entering further co-creation process with the full network.

- In one case, around the second month of the proposal writing, the lead partner was encouraging the partners of the core group to think directly about the WPs. However, according to the lump-sum approach there are work areas inside of which there are WPs. **Jumping immediately to the WPs puts the partners into a kind of a box**, thus creating an additional future task of connecting the boxes into work areas. A solution was found during one of the

core group meetings to step back and think about the bigger picture (the impact, etc.) and use that to form the work in WPs and work areas.

- **Smaller organisations are working hard to understand technical dimensions** of the call whereas larger partners have a much greater capacity and support services to understand more quickly the new technical obligations of HE. The difference of MAA is also relevant here: certain types of partners tend to be larger and have more experience and have developed specific support offices/individuals to support people who are doing the proposal writing (particularly universities, larger research institutions).

- One proposal included **a partner** that throughout the development process **did not directly participate in meetings**, but another proposal partner took up their representation. This can be accepted for a relevant partner that shows full reliability and capability when the project starts, as this was the case here.

- **Completing the budget** is a challenge and unexpected issues may arise, like adjusting staff costs of very different types of partners, as a MAA proposal may probably have. The new mechanism of lump-sum projects in HE needs careful attention not to be misinterpreted, including planning work package completion terms to ensure financial viability for all partners along the project, and managing more complex budget templates.

- The topic of this proposal is complex enough without the **MAA**, which **seems added at the end and disconnected from the rest of the scope**. It is a **challenge to address all topic expectations with the budget available**. This also conditions the distribution of partners considering the range of staff costs across Europe.

- Partners might be **contributing to proposals in many different ways and styles**, for example, a partner may write little but bring relevant knowledge, references, contacts, case study sites, etc., and another may be contributing in stages, with long gaps in between. As a **coordinator, adjusting and aligning everyone** as much as possible and making out the best of all partners is a way to address this.

- One proposal needed and included a very large world-level international partner, bringing strength but also difficulties, e.g. due to their own internal procedures involving extra validation of other partners, staff costs conditioning the overall budget, or simply due to the strong pre-existing organisational work and public relations culture potentially limiting the partner's flexibility in

adjusting to the overall ethos of the emerging consortium. **Cope, be flexible, adapt and solve, when this is a key partner** you do not want to miss, and use a ‘safety measure’ with another partner that could take up the role in case of an unexpected drop out (that did not occur in this example).

- A proposal had a **partner exiting a few weeks to submission** for external reasons, in this case the exiting partner helped in finding a replacement in the same country, and this actually ended in adding extra and unique multi-actor expertise that otherwise the proposal would not have had.

- The way in which different call topics require the multi-actor approach to be applied can be challenging. For instance, the text of a call topic implies that the consortium should be composed of advisors. However, this seems to be in some ways working against the MAA. It raises a question **how to apply the MAA** according to other elements of the definition of MAA, **if the composition of the consortium seems to be of less importance according to the call text.**

- Often in proposals, many of the partners involved are the usual suspects, since there is a limited number of relevant organisations that might be engaged. Still, it is challenging to decide if more effort should be made to engage some harder to reach partners who are not the usual suspects. **If less experienced partners are invited to join the consortium, the project coordinator must be ready to add extra effort and time** to get the less experienced partners on board, while not hindering the progress of more experienced partners.

- A proposal had a strategy to involve and **share with partners the overall approach and concept note close to one month to submission**, when the first consortium meeting was organised. At this stage, also a partner outside of Europe (recommended, not required in the call topic) was introduced to all partners. This approach **generated momentum and ‘excitement’** of the partners in the last weeks, when their involvement became highest.

- In one case, **MAA tasks were allocated to partners that did not even know what MA was at the start** of the proposal preparation. This has its risks, but it is a certain positive approach. The lead of the MAA WP has an ‘observer’ task to allow monitoring and follow up of all partners’ MAA activities all along the project.

- It might be the case that **a final submitted proposal has a good definition of MAA tasks, but that it is difficult to make clear how the task would match with end users’ needs.**

- In proposals, partners may not achieve a general overview of the whole project dynamics and the role of different actors. Also, due to the topic, some partners might be very focussed on their part of the work, and not interested in the overall approach. Still, **in the given timeframe of a Horizon call, it is sometimes not possible to involve the partners more.** Everybody has a lot on their plates and that does not allow for more contribution. At the end **the personal big effort and interest in the submission of the two coordinators might be what ensures** the best possible proposal submission. Due to the active coordination approach, partners were less active, and the personal effort had to be big.

6. CONCLUSION

The emerging proposals' report has presented relevant tips, approaches, and methodologies that were gathered from regular interviews with participants taking part in the writing of three Horizon Europe proposals between early autumn 2023 and February 2024. A special attention was paid to the multi-actor elements that were present in the preparation of all three proposals. The report also identified most significant challenges that were present during the preparation process of multi-actor proposals and adapted solutions.

All three proposals highlight the importance of a structured collaboration between the project leader and the partners, as well as the need for an open dialogue between the whole group of partners involved in the proposal development, which can be structured in different ways. The cases also suggest that the lead partner must have a strategy for involving other partners at later stages of the proposal development process. They also reveal valuable examples of the use of digital tools for the content development, organisation of meetings, as well as administrative purposes. At the same time, the cases also openly show room for development of even more structured tools and approaches for the purposes of making the proposal development more inclusive and multi-actor.

Some challenges encountered by the interviewees reveal that the administrative and writing tasks must be tackled in an interlinked way. The report also brings to consideration the need to pay attention to individual qualities of partners, including their prior experience and the size of the organisation. Finally, the need to facilitate a multi-actor environment from the first steps of proposal development is being highlighted.

7. ANNEXES

7.1. Summary guidelines used during the search of emerging proposals

Objectives of the emerging proposals review

- Provide insights during the emerging multi - actor proposal development of use for pathway definition and for other WP3 activities as well.
- Follow- up 5 cases of proposal development in a regular monthly basis between October – February, the preparatory period for submissions on the CL6 February calls.
- Capture “live” impressions, statements on what happens as the proposal takes form and completes.
- Reduce to the very minimum needed the time required by the team of the 5 emerging proposals in this busy period.

Procedure and benefits

- Around the 15th every month (5 - month period Oct - Feb) interview for a rigorous maximum of 20' the actor participating in an emerging proposal. First and last meetings 45' of duration for more in- depth.
- Interview to be recorded only for use in WP3 and deleted when the analysis is completed.
- The 5 emerging proposals will be on 5 different topics.
- Interviews to be based on a progressive questionnaire pre - defined by WP3 team, with different questions every month. Live case of multi - actor proposal development will be the focus of the questions.
- Optional (if interviewee is interested): Research can benefit of becoming action - reviewing oriented during the interview process, this way the interviewer can act as an external reviewer and adviser along the preparation of the proposal.

Confidentiality and absence of CoI

- 1 single interviewer, same person in all 5 interviews who will have no personal conflict of interest in that topic in terms of research / application.
- Interview to be recorded only for use in WP3 and deleted when the analysis is completed.
- The 5 emerging proposals will be on 5 different topics.
- Topics and organisations interviewed will not be disclosed until the February submission deadline (or never disclosed if asked).
- Information extracted from the interviews will be captured in anonymous form without any names or organisations mentioned.
- The 5 emerging proposals will be kept in the highest confidentiality possible within PREMIERE WP3 team.

7.2. Interview guidelines used for the follow-up of emerging proposals

PREMIERE interview guidelines for T3.2: Pathways for MA proposal development adapted to particular contexts

The objective of the interviews is to follow-up 5 cases of proposal development on a regular monthly basis between October 2023 – February 2024, the preparatory period for submissions on the HE Cluster 6 February calls. The interviews will capture “live” impressions, statements on what happens as the proposal takes form and completes.

Interviewing procedure

The interviews will take place around the 15th every month (5-month period Oct-Feb).

Interviewees: actors participating in an emerging proposal (either coordinator or a partner with an active role in the proposal preparation)

Interview length: Maximum of 20'. First and last meetings 45' of duration for more in-depth questions.

Interviews will be recorded only for use in WP3 and deleted when the analysis is completed.

The 5 emerging proposals will be on 5 different topics.

The interviewers will keep as undisclosed as possible the details of the proposal, even to the rest of the WP3 team, until the call deadline in February.

Introductory questions (*only for the first round of interviews*)

1. Please briefly describe the project proposal you are currently working on, particularly focusing on terms of how the multi-actor approach is deployed!
2. How long ago do did you start thinking about this proposal? Is this: i) an all-new proposal, ii) based on some previous partners, or is it iii) a restructuring of a previously formed consortium of partners?
3. Please tell us a little bit about the project consortium that you have gathered so far to work on the proposal (the number of partners, the organisations

they represent, geographical distribution, number of novices, experienced and follower partners involved). What proportion of partners were identified at least 6-months before submission (before 1 August)?

4. How did you identify the multi-actor composition of your consortium? How did you search for and find the multi-actor partners needed? Are any of them challenging? Do you keep an open space for these in the coming weeks?
5. Could you give an overview of the planned proposal writing process, for instance, the regularity of the meetings expected, the intended structure of the meetings and which project partners are expected to take part in which meetings? Are you using specific digital tools for proposal preparation (Cloud-drive, Mural or alike, shared chat (Teams, Slack..)? Are all multi-actor partners confident with that?
6. What are your expectations of the proposal writing process and the partners involved?
7. Are there any challenges you already foresee? Have you thought of any solutions to mitigate these challenges if they arise?

Timeline related questions (complementary questions that may be used at certain stages but not in all meetings)

8. In what parts of proposal writing are you currently more focused?
9. Have you now completed the pivotal early decisions in the consortium (e.g. partners composition, WP distribution, methods, general budget distribution)?
10. *(To ask in December)* Do you think it would be useful if we confidentially review a consolidated draft of your proposal in terms of multi-actor approach? When would it be a good moment to do so?

Questions regarding the involvement of the partners

11. How would you describe the current involvement of the partner organisations? Do you see different degrees of involvement regarding multi-actor kind of partners? How is (are you) proposal coordination dealing with it? Do you see an evolution from previous months?

12. Could you give specific examples that show the degree of involvement of the project partners?
13. What has worked particularly well in relation to engaging the partners in the proposal multi-actor development?
14. Can you name the actor groups that your proposal involves²? Do you plan to add any later? Do you miss any?

Actors as listed in the MA requirements of the HE Cluster 6 work programme:

1. <i>Researchers</i>	7. <i>Food and bioeconomy businesses</i>
2. <i>Farmers / farmers' groups and associations</i>	8. <i>Other businesses</i>
3. <i>Foresters / foresters' groups and associations</i>	9. <i>Consumer associations</i>
4. <i>Aquaculture producers</i>	10. <i>Local communities</i>
5. <i>Fishers / fishers' groups and associations</i>	11. <i>Citizens</i>
6. <i>Advisors</i>	12. <i>Civil society</i>
	13. <i>Civil society organisations including NGOs</i>
	14. <i>Government representatives</i>

Questions regarding the proposal writing process

15. How would you describe the current state of the project proposal (please be specific on the multi-actor developments since our last interview)?
16. Please describe concrete activities that have taken place over the last month towards the development of the proposal and tell us more about the involvement of different types of partners in this process!
17. Has there been a multi-actor approach to proposal writing? How? And, if there has not, why?
18. Have there been any challenges related to the proposal writing lately? If yes, which steps have you taken or plan to take to overcome these challenges?
19. What has gone particularly well in relation to the proposal writing over the last month of project preparation? Describe any successful arrangements that have helped to involve the project partners in the process!

² As they are listed in the MA requirements of the Cluster 6 Work Programme.

20. What are the next activities planned towards completing the project proposal?
21. How are you particularly addressing the requirement that “practitioners and (end) users are to be involved, not as a study-object, but to use their practical and local knowledge and/or entrepreneurial skills to develop solutions and create ‘co-ownership’ of results for (end-) users and practitioners”?

Questions regarding administrative and technical management process (*this section to be opened in the December interview*)

22. Which have been the main administrative and/or technical tasks that you have undertaken during the last month?
23. What has been your progress in relation to distributing administrative roles among the project partners? Are you exploring diversity of partner types (subcontractor, third-party, cascade funding)? Please briefly describe the actions taken over the last month!
24. Have you experienced any drawbacks or challenges in relation to partners’ capacity to fulfil the administrative and/or technical tasks related to the proposal writing? Do you have partners that are in need of extra support for these aspects? How do they relate to multi-actor?
25. What are the next administrative/technical steps foreseen?

Closing questions (*only for the last round of interviews*)

26. Which have been the main success factors during the proposal writing process?
27. Which have been the main drawbacks and challenges that hampered the overall writing process of the proposal? Which steps were taken to overcome these?
28. How would you describe the current state of involvement of the project partners, if compared to the beginning of the proposal writing? Can you give specific examples that highlight the change in the partners’ degree of involvement?

29. How satisfied are you with the process and the current outcome? Do you think you have achieved a satisfactory result in terms of multi-actor process of proposal development³? Tell us one thing you could have still improved!
30. Will your MAA ensure that “outcomes are shared more extensively”? Will you effectively reach the “(end-) users of the project results” “all over the course of the project”?
31. Which aspects related to the involvement of the partners, the proposal writing process, and the administrative and technical management process could have been done differently and possibly more efficiently? Why?

³ The multi-actor approach described here - a form of responsible R&I, aims to make the R&I process and its outcomes more reliable, demand-driven, shared and relevant to society.

Periodic quantitative assessment of the proposal writing process (to be completed at the end of each interview)

1. On a scale of 1-10, how would you on average assess **the current engagement** of most project partners in the proposal writing?

1 Extremely disengaged	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Extremely engaged
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2. On a scale of 1-10, how would you rate **how relevant have multi-actor aspects been** in the proposal preparation over the last months?

1 Very poor	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Excellent
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3. On a scale of 1-10, how would you assess **the consortium’s ability to overcome challenges** experienced in the process of proposal writing?

1 Very poor	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Excellent
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4. On a scale of 1-10, how would you assess **the clarity and accuracy of the proposal organisation and development process?**

1 Very poor	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Excellent
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7.3. Reporting table used to register the information collected at each interview with the emerging proposals

		Interview number				
		1	2	3	4	5
Interview date						
Consortium	Partner recruitment					
	MA partner types planned					
	OGs in proposal					
	Process & Development					
	Partners' involvement					
	Main challenges					
	Other comments / Impressions					
Writing	Steps achieved					
	Content development					
	Relevant methods & tools					
	Development of the MAA					
	Main challenges					
	Other comments / Impressions					
Administration	Budget co-creation					
	Partner input					
	Needed clarifications					
	Main challenges					
	Other comments / Impressions					
	Miscellaneous					
Scores	1 - Partner's engagement					
	2 - Relevance of MAA in this period					
	3 - Overcoming challenges					
	4 - Clarity of the process					
	Recording link					

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